

AN ANALYSIS OF DISCOURSE MARKERS USED BY STUDENTS IN WRITING PROCEDURE TEXT AT SMK NEGERI 3 GOWA

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ABSTRACT: This study focused on the use of discourse markers by students in writing procedure texts. The aim was to identify the types of discourse markers that were most often used in writing procedure texts. A descriptive quantitative method was employed for this research. The instrument used was a procedure text writing test. In this study, the researcher collected data in the form of 30 procedure texts made by students of SMK Negeri 3 Gowa. This research used types of discourse markers based on Fraser's (2006) taxonomy to analyze the types of use of discourse markers found in writing procedural texts. The results of the research showed that all types of discourse markers were used in students' written procedure texts. Temporal markers were most often used by students, namely (83.7%), followed by elaborative markers (5.6%), contrastive markers (3.9%), and the least were inferential markers (3.2%). This meant that when writing procedure texts, students often explained the sequence or steps. Apart from that, the results of this research also revealed that the majority of students were able to use discourse markers correctly in writing procedure texts..

Keywords: Discourse Markers, Procedure Text, Writing, Analysis, Linguistic features

Аннотация: Данное исследование было сосредоточено на использовании студентами дискурсивных маркеров при написании процедурных текстов. Целью было выявить типы дискурсивных маркеров, которые чаще всего использовались при написании процедурных текстов. Для этого исследования был использован описательный количественный метод. В качестве инструмента использовался тест на написание текста процедуры. В этом исследовании исследователь собрал данные в виде 30 текстов процедур, составленных студентами SMK Negeri 3 Gowa. В этом исследовании использовались типы дискурсивных маркеров, основанные на таксономии Фрейзера (2006), для анализа типов использования дискурсивных маркеров, обнаруженных при написании процедурных текстов. Результаты исследования показали, что в письменных процедурных текстах студентов используются все виды дискурсивных маркеров. Студенты чаще всего использовали временные маркеры (83,7%), за ними следовали уточняющие маркеры (5,6%), контрастивные маркеры (3,9%) и реже всего - инференциальные

маркеры (3,2%). Это означало, что при написании текстов процедур студенты часто объясняли последовательность или шаги. Кроме того, результаты данного исследования также показали, что большинство студентов смогли правильно использовать дискурсивные маркеры при написании процедурных текстов.

Ключевые слова: дискурсивные маркеры, процедурный текст, письмо, анализ, лингвистические особенности.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot talabalar tomonidan protsedura matnlarini yozishda nutq belgilaridan foydalanishga qaratilgan. Maqsad protsedura matnlarini yozishda eng ko‘p ishlatiladigan nutq belgilarining turlarini aniqlash edi. Ushbu tadqiqot uchun tavsiflovchi miqdoriy usul ishlatilgan. Amaldagi asbob protsedura matnini yozish testi edi. Ushbu tadqiqotda tadqiqotchi SMK Negeri 3 Gowa talabalar tomonidan tuzilgan 30 ta protsedura matni shaklida ma'lumotlarni to'pladi. Ushbu tadqiqot protsessual matnlarni yozishda uchraydigan nutq belgilaridan foydalanish turlarini tahlil qilish uchun Freyzer (2006) taksonomiyasiga asoslangan nutq belgilarining turlaridan foydalangan. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, talabalar yozma protsedura matnlarida barcha turdagi nutq belgilaridan foydalanilgan. Vaqtinchalik markerlar ko'pincha talabalar tomonidan qo'llanilgan, ya'ni (83,7%), undan keyingi o'rinlarda ishlab chiqilgan markerlar (5,6%), kontrastli belgilar (3,9%) va eng kami inferensial belgilar (3,2%). Bu shuni anglatadiki, protsedura matnlarini yozishda talabalar ko'pincha ketma-ketlik yoki bosqichlarni tushuntirib berishdi. Bundan tashqari, ushbu tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, talabalarning aksariyati protsedura matnlarini yozishda nutq belgilaridan to'g'ri foydalana olgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Diskurs belgilari, protsedura matni, yozish, tahlil, lingvistik xususiyatlar

INTRODUCTION

Language is the main resource used by humans to communicate with other people around them to express ideas. There are several languages used in the world to communicate, one of which is English which is used as an international language (Pratiwi, 2021). English is not something new for Indonesian students because English is a mandatory subject that they must study at school and university. In teaching English, there are four skills that are learned, namely listening, speaking, reading and writing. Among the four skills learned, there are still many students who cannot use English well, they still make mistakes in using English, especially in writing.

In the academic world, writing is an important skill that is most needed in several activities carried out by students during their education. According to Sohaya (2018), writing is one of the language skills that students must master in the process of learning English as a Foreign Language. Writing requires more than just the production of words and phrases. In writing, we must be able to produce a series of words and phrases that are grammatically connected and logically related. To clarify ideas, students must of course write instructions to reveal what they mean in the next segment. So students must be able to use connectors in their writing sequentially to write something

There are several connectors that can be used in writing sentences, texts or even essays. One of them is discourse markers. Discourse markers are connectors that can unify a piece of writing and can also unify different parts of a text or sentence. Discourse markers are words or expressions that are used to connect, organize, manage, and control communication both oral and written. Discourse markers are linguistic features that are useful for stringing or tying several things together (Wahid & Suyitno, 2020). Discourse markers function to control the spoken and written communication that we do. Besides that, discourse markers are used to start and end a sentence or phrase in a conversation. Based on Fraser (2006), taxonomy Discourse Markers are divided into four types: Contrastive, Elaborative, Inferential and Temporal. The use of discourse markers can connect transitions with suitable words to make them cohesive. Discourse markers are often used in several types of texts, one of which is procedure text.

Procedure text is text that contains information about how to make or do something. Procedure text is one type of text that is often studied by students. Procedure text can make it easier for us to create something easily so that what we want can be easily achieved (Prayogi et al., 2022). Procedure texts aim to provide instructions about the steps in doing something so that writing them requires discourse markers in writing

Based on observations made by researcher at the Textile Department of SMK Negeri 3 Gowa, researcher saw a lot of discourse markers used by students in procedure texts, so researcher are interested in examining related discourse markers to find out What types of discourse markers do students use in their procedure text writing at SMK Negeri 3 Gowa? This research focuses on analyzing the types of discourse markers used in procedure texts.

METHOD

This research was conducted using descriptive quantitative research. Descriptive research aimed to clarify or describe a situation, event, object, or anything related to a variable that could be explained either with numbers or words. The population of this study was students of class XII majoring in Textiles at SMK Negeri 3 Gowa, which consisted of two classes. The total number of students majoring in textiles was 52 students researcher determined the sample using simple random sampling techniques. All populations have the same opportunity to be selected as a sample The sampling technique was carried out using a lottery system with a total of 52 students,, so that the sample for this research is only 30 students. The instrument that was used in that research was a written test. The researcher asked students to write procedure texts based on the topics that were given. Data collection in this research was conducted through written tests. The written test in this research was in the form of procedure texts written by students based on the topics provided by the researcher. Through the writing test data, the researcher observed the types of discourse markers used by students, how many discourse markers were used, and which ones were used more frequently. The steps for analyzing student data using discourse markers in procedural text writing were as follows: analyzing students' procedural text writing based on discourse markers, tabulating students' writing

using discourse markers based on their writing, and calculating percentages. The researcher used the following formula to find percentages of items and concluded the results

$$P = \frac{f}{n} \times 100\%$$

P = the percentage of the result

f = the frequency of students use discourse marker

n = total amount of the sample

RESULTS

Based on the research conducted at SMK Negeri 3 Gowa, researcher found 126 discourse marker type words in 30 procedure texts written by students. the data obtained by researcher can be seen in the following table:

Table 1. The data of the students procedure text

NO	Types Discourse Markers	Frequency	Percentage
	Constactive Markers	5	3.9%
	Elaborative Markers	7	5.6%
	Inverential Markers	4	3.2%
	Temporal Markers	110	87.3%
	Total	126	100%

Contrastive Markers

Contrastive discourse markers are the first type of discourse markers that students used in writing procedure texts.. Based on table 1 above, the total contrastive markers used by students in writing procedure texts is 5 (3.9%). In this research, the findings show that students in writing procedure texts use contrastive discourse markers.. The contrastive markers contained in the students' written procedure text can be seen in the following table.

Table 2. The use of Contrastive Markers

NO	Word of Contrastive Markers	Frecuency
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1.	But	3
2.	However	2

Elaborative Markers

Elaborative markers are the second type of discourse that students used in writing procedure texts. Based on table 1 above, the total contrastive markers used by students in writing procedure texts is 7 (5.6%). After analyzing the students' data, the researcher found that the text procedure writing consisted of these discourse markers. The forms of elaborative markers that appear in the text procedure writing can be seen in the following table.

Table 3. The use of Elaborative Markers

NO	Word of Elaborative Markers	Frecuency
1.	Also	2
2.	In adition	1
3.	Or	4

Inferential Markers

Inferential Markers are the third type that is least used by students in writing procedure texts. Based on table 1 above, the total inferential markers used by students in writing procedure texts is 4 (3.2%). After analyzing the data, the researcher found that only 4 inferential markers were used in writing the text, which can be seen in the following table.

Table 4. The use of Inferential Markers

NO	Word of Inferential Markers	Frecuency
1.	Because	1
2.	Thus	3

Temporal Markers

Temporal markers are the last type of discourse markers. Temporal discourse markers have the highest rank of discourse markers used by students in writing procedure texts. Based on table 1 above, the total temporal markers used by students in writing procedure texts is 110 occurrences and the percentage (83.7 The contrastive markers contained in the students' written procedure text can be seen in the following table.

Table 5. The use of Temporal Markers

NO	Word of Temporal Markers	Frecuency
1.	Then	55
2.	After	16
3.	Before	1
4.	Finally	7
5.	First	19
6.	Meanwhile	2
7.	Second	9
8.	When	1

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of this study, the research findings show that four types of discourse markers based on Fraser's (2006) taxonomy are used by students in writing procedure texts at SMK Negeri 3 Gowa. The main finding shows that students tend to use temporal discourse markers in writing procedure texts, with the percentage of usage reaching 87.3%. In addition, elaborative discourse markers were used to a lesser extent with a percentage of 5.6%, followed by contrastive markers at 3.9%, and inferential markers at 3.2%.

As mentioned earlier, temporal markers are frequently used by students in writing procedure texts, this is because students tend to focus on explaining the time sequence or steps in the process described and due to the instructional nature of procedure texts that require a clear sequence in the explanation of each step. This finding is in line with previous research (Rabab'ah et al., 2022), who found that the large number of temporal discourse markers used in his research was due to the writing topic that directed students to use this type of dicourse markers. The most used temporal marker by students is the word then, because the use of “then” makes the steps clear and easy to understand, helping

readers to follow the instructions chronologically. This is in line with previous research which found that the word then was often used by participants to connect propositions that expressed time sequence in their descriptive essays (Wahid & Suyitno, 2020).

The second frequent type of discourse markers used by students in writing procedural texts is elaborative markers. Elaborative markers are used to provide additional information or relevant examples related to the steps or instructions that have been given previously. According to Nirwana (2022), elaborative markers are used to connect additional contexts that are the same as what has happened before.. The use of elaborative markers such as “also” helps to convey additional instructions or relevant examples. This finding is in line with previous research, especially (Syahdanis, 2020) who found that in his research on argumentative text writing, “also” was found the most and functions to provide a lot of reasons, arguments, and add information.

Contrastive discourse markers in this study are the third discourse markers found in procedure text writing. Contrastive markers are used to show the difference or contrast between opposite steps or instructions in the described process. The use of contrastive markers such as “but” helps readers understand the difference between two conflicting steps or instructions in the procedure text. In the results of (Lu et al., 2022) research showed that students used the discourse marker “but” to compare and contrast one idea with another and express opposing opinions.

The most common type of discourse marker used in writing procedure texts is the inferential marker. Inferential markers are used to draw conclusions or implications from information that has been conveyed previously. According to Raputri et al. (2022), inferential discourse markers can be interpreted as discourse markers that function to convey messages such as the conclusion or inference of a sentence. Although rarely used, the use of inferential markers such as “because” helps students convey the cause-and-effect relationship or conclusion of the instructions that have been given.

CONCLUSION

For the results of this study, it can be concluded that all types of discourse markers based on Fraser's 2006 taxonomy are used by students in writing procedural texts at SMK Negeri 3 Gowa, majoring in textiles. Temporal discourse markers emerged as the most frequently employed markers by students. This preference can be attributed to the inherent requirement of procedural texts to provide a clear and sequential presentation of steps or instructions. Among temporal markers, "then" stood out as the most commonly used, facilitating chronological clarity in procedural descriptions. Elaborative markers, though less prevalent compared to temporal markers, play a crucial role in enriching procedural texts by providing additional information. Markers such as "or" serve to supplement instructions or offer relevant examples, thereby enhancing the clarity and comprehensiveness of procedural descriptions. Following elaborative markers, students utilized contrastive markers to emphasize differences or contrasts between various steps or instructions in procedural texts. Markers like "but" help elucidate opposing actions or

choices, contributing to a nuanced understanding of procedural processes. Lastly, inferential markers, while less frequently used, serve to convey cause-and-effect relationships or draw conclusions from the instructions provided. Although relatively rare, these markers, such as "because," contribute to the overall coherence and logical development of procedural descriptions. For future researchers who want to conduct similar research, it would be more meaningful if they develop a theoretical framework from previous theories, either contained in this study or other references, to analyze other types of texts.

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